

Relativity Theories, Einstein Thought Experiments Revisited

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1 Introduction

Since Galileo scientists were conscious of the necessity that all the laws in physics hold good whatever the motion of an inertial reference frame. When it has been shown it was not the case for the equation of propagation of electromagnetic waves with the use of the Newtonian rule, there was a challenge to find the way to solve this problem. Everyone knows how Einstein found his way to his relativity theory. Far fewer people have the knowledge of existence of Young-Sea Huang relativity theory. In this paper we will compare these two relativity theories with Einstein Thought Experiments. Since the reader may not be aware of the conceptual theory of Young-Sea Huang relativity, it is recommended to first read the documents in reference [1] [2] [3].

2 Relativity Concepts

To see the difference of concepts between these two theories of relativity it is necessary to understand how they dealt with the displacement of a moving body. Let's do this with the example of a particle which is measured in two inertial reference frames, one chosen to be at rest and the other to have a relative velocity V with respect to the first one.

In Einstein view the motion of a particle is measured simultaneously in the two frames by the coordinates in space and time of the particle. This means that the position and the velocity of a particle, at a precise instant, is well known also in the two frames. This view is in complete opposition to Heisenberg's uncertainty principle of quantum mechanics and explain why Einstein theory and quantum mechanics can't merge to give an overall theory from the infinite to the microscopic. To put it succinctly, the transformation from one frame to the other is done in the space-time coordinates.

In Young-Sea Huang view it is the definite value of the energy-momentum of the particle which is known at a precise instant in both reference frames, taking into account the relative motion between the two frames. The precise position of the particle, in the two reference frames, is not known. To put it succinctly, the transformation from one frame to the other is done in the velocity space only. The speed of light is taken as a reference velocity in the transformation, but it is not a requirement in itself. Using this transformation, Young-Sea Huang theory is compatible with quantum mechanics.

In the following we proceed with more details on both transformations to highlight the differences.

3 Young-Sea Huang Transformation

Young-Sea Huang transformation is described in the following. In relation to a reference frame X, let us consider a particle of velocity v at a moment t , this particle will move with a virtual spatial displacement $\delta x = v\delta t$, during a virtual duration $\delta t > 0$.

We also define $\delta x^0 = c\delta t$, because the speed of light c is assumed to be invariant. Thus at this moment t , the state of movement of this particle, in relation to the reference frame X, can be characterized by infinitesimal displacement at 4 variables $\delta x^\alpha = (\delta x^0, \delta x)$. With this matrix of 4 variables $\delta x^\alpha (\alpha = 0, 1, 2, 3)$, the velocity v is defined at the same time.

It should be noted that, according to the uncertainty principle of quantum mechanics, it is impossible to know with certainty the position x of a particle, when its speed is determined exactly. That is, when its state of motion δx^α is exactly specified.

The principle of uncertainty does not, however, preclude the assumption that the particle is at an unknown position when its state of motion δx^α is known exactly. However, the particle is located somewhere, which cannot be determined without interfering with its state of motion. It is not allowed to specify simultaneously the exact values for both the state of movement δx^α , and the position x of the particle. Here, to have the state of displacement δx^α , it is not necessary to specify the exact value of $x^\alpha = (ct, x)$.

Suppose that an inertial referential \bar{S} moves with a constant speed V in relation to another inertial referential S. At a moment t arbitrary, a particle has a state of motion δx^α in relation to the reference system S with the Cartesian coordinates X. This particle has the corresponding state of motion $\delta \bar{x}^\mu$ in relation to the reference frame \bar{S} with the Cartesian coordinates of the \bar{X} .

It is important to note that both X and \bar{X} coordinate systems have the same units of measurement for position and duration.

Suppose there is a linear transformation for the state of displacement between the two inertial reference frames, i.e.:

$$\delta x^\alpha = a^\alpha_\mu(X, \bar{X})\delta \bar{x}^\mu \quad (\alpha, \mu = 0, 1, 2, 3) \quad (1)$$

Using these notations, the relativistic transformation of the displacement state δx^α can be obtained by :

$$\delta x^0 = \gamma(\delta \bar{x}^0 + \beta\delta \bar{x}^1) \quad (2)$$

$$\delta x^1 = \gamma(\beta\delta \bar{x}^0 + \delta \bar{x}^1) \quad (3)$$

$$\delta x^2 = \delta \bar{x}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\delta x^3 = \delta \bar{x}^3 \quad (5)$$

With $\gamma = (1 - \beta^2)^{-1/2}$ et $\beta = V/c$

It is important to note that the infinitesimal amounts δx^α are not the differential of the actual coordinates x^α . Displacement δx^α is the state of displacement at a time t and does not correspond to a spatial displacement $x(t_2) - x(t_1)$ which is defined as the difference in positions $x(t_2)$ and $x(t_1)$ at two instant t_2 and t_1 respectively. Lorentz differential

transformation δx^α is not equivalent to Lorentz transformation of space-time coordinates x^α .

By the relativistic transformation above, we obtain the formulas for the addition of speeds:

$$\gamma_v = \gamma \gamma_{\bar{v}} \left(1 + \beta \frac{\bar{v}^1}{c}\right) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{v^1}{c} = \frac{(\beta + \frac{\bar{v}^1}{c})}{(1 + \beta \frac{\bar{v}^1}{c})} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{v^2}{c} = \frac{\bar{v}^2/c}{\gamma(1 + \beta \frac{\bar{v}^1}{c})} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{v^3}{c} = \frac{\bar{v}^3/c}{\gamma(1 + \beta \frac{\bar{v}^1}{c})} \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma_v = (1 - (v/c)^2)^{-1/2} \quad (10)$$

$$\gamma_{\bar{v}} = (1 - (\bar{v}/c)^2)^{-1/2} \quad (11)$$

We can see that when the speed V is small in front of c , then the addition of the speeds is of Galilean nature. According to this new relativistic transformation, the laws of physics are rendered invariant by the transformation of physical quantities, instead of space-time coordinates.

4 Einstein Transformation

In his 1905 paper [4], Einstein thought about simultaneity of events. In order to not introduce errors, here is the original text of Einstein paper.

“Let there be given a stationary rigid rod; and let its length be l as measured by a measuring-rod which is also stationary. We now imagine the axis of the rod lying along the axis of x of the stationary system of co-ordinates, and that a uniform motion of parallel translation with velocity v along the axis of x in the direction of increasing x is then imparted to the rod. We now inquire as to the length of the moving rod, and imagine its length to be ascertained by the following two operations:

(a) The observer moves together with the given measuring-rod and the rod to be measured, and measures the length of the rod directly by superposing the measuring-rod, in just the same way as if all three were at rest.

(b) By means of stationary clocks set up in the stationary system and synchronizing in accordance with the definition in the above reference, the observer ascertains at what points of the stationary system the two ends of the rod to be measured are located at a definite time. The distance between these two points, measured by the measuring-rod already employed, which in this case is at rest, is also a length which may be designated “the length of the rod.”

In accordance with the principle of relativity the length to be discovered by the operation (a)—we will call it “the length of the rod in the moving system”—must be equal to the length l of the stationary rod. The length to be discovered by the operation (b) we will call “the length of the (moving) rod in the stationary system.” This we shall determine on the basis of our two principles, and we shall find that it differs from l .

Current kinematics tacitly assumes that the lengths determined by these two operations are precisely equal, or in other words, that a moving rigid body at the epoch t may in geometrical respects be perfectly represented by the same body at rest in a definite position. We imagine further that at the two ends A and B of the rod, clocks are placed which synchronize with the clocks of the stationary system, that is to say that their indications correspond at any instant to the “time of the stationary system” at the places where they happen to be. These clocks are therefore “synchronous in the stationary system.”

We imagine further that with each clock there is a moving observer, and that these observers apply to both clocks the criterion established in the reference for the synchronization of two clocks. Let a ray of light depart from A at the time t_A , let it be reflected at B at the time t_B , and reach A again at the time t'_A . Taking into consideration the principle of the constancy of the velocity of light we find that

$$t_B - t_A = \frac{\tau_{AB}}{c - v} \quad (12)$$

and

$$t'_B - t'_A = \frac{\tau_{AB}}{c + v} \quad (13)$$

where τ_{AB} denotes the length of the moving rod—measured in the stationary system. Observers moving with the moving rod would thus find that the two clocks were not synchronous, while observers in the stationary system would declare the clocks to be synchronous. So we see that we cannot attach any absolute signification to the concept of simultaneity, but that two events which, viewed from a system of co-ordinates, are simultaneous, can no longer be looked upon as simultaneous events when envisaged from a system which is in motion relatively to that system”.

This thought experiment is not a problem of simultaneity of events, but just a problem of “rendez-vous”. When one has to catch a train at a precise moment in space, knowing how the train is going, he must adapt the duration of his travel time taking into account the length of the path to go to the station.

In Einstein document the part about mathematics is called “Theory of the Transformation of Co-ordinates and Times from a Stationary System to another System in Uniform Motion of Translation Relatively to the Former”.

The derivation of the transformation is the following, with the original text in Einstein paper. “Let us in “stationary” space take two systems of co-ordinates, i.e. two systems, each of three rigid material lines, perpendicular to one another, and issuing from a point. Let the axes of X of the two systems coincide, and their axes of Y and Z respectively be parallel. Let each system be provided with a rigid measuring-rod and a number of clocks, and let the two measuring-rods, and likewise all the clocks of the two systems, be in all respects alike. Now to the origin of one of the two systems (k) let a constant velocity v be imparted in the direction of the increasing x of the other stationary system (K), and let this velocity be communicated to the axes of the co-ordinates, the relevant measuring-rod, and the clocks. To any time of the stationary system K there then will correspond a definite position of the axes of the moving system, and from reasons of symmetry we are entitled to assume that the motion of k may be such that the axes of the moving system are at the time t (this “ t ” always denotes a time of the stationary system) parallel to the axes of the stationary system.

We now imagine space to be measured from the stationary system K by means of the stationary measuring rod, and also from the moving system k by means of the measuring rod moving with it; and that we thus obtain the co-ordinates x, y, z , and ξ, η, ζ , respectively.

Further, let the time t of the stationary system be determined for all points thereof at which there are clocks by means of light signals in the manner indicated in chap 1(of the reference document); similarly let the time τ of the moving system be determined for all points of the moving system at which there are clocks at rest relatively to that system by applying the method, given in chap 1(of the reference document), of light signals between the points at which the latter clocks are located.

To any system of values x, y, z, t , which completely defines the place and time of an event in the stationary system, there belongs a system of values ξ, η, ζ, τ , determining that event relatively to the system k , and our task is now to find the system of equations connecting these quantities. In the first place it is clear that the equations must be linear on account of the properties of homogeneity which we attribute to space and time.

If we place $x'=x-vt$, it is clear that a point at rest in the system k must have a system of values x', y, z , independent of time. We first define τ as a function of x', y, z , and t . To do this we have to express in equations that τ is nothing else than the summary of the data of clocks at rest in system k , which have been synchronized according to the rule given in chap 1(of the reference document). From the origin of system k let a ray be emitted at the time τ_0 along the X-axis to x' , and at the time τ_1 be reflected thence to the origin of the co-ordinates, arriving there at the time τ_2 ; we then must have $\frac{1}{2}(\tau_0 + \tau_2) = \tau_1, \dots$ ".

The task was then "to find the system of equations connecting these quantities". Einstein obtains finally:

$$\tau = \phi(v)\beta(t - vx/c^2) \tag{14}$$

$$\xi = \phi(v)\beta(x - vt) \tag{15}$$

$$\eta = \phi(v)y \tag{16}$$

$$\zeta = \phi(v)z \tag{17}$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} \tag{18}$$

There is no question about the reasoning and the results obtained by Einstein with the above assumptions. He found in the end the well known set of equations that transform the position of a point given in space-time coordinates from one reference frame to another one in motion. We can see from Einstein text that, to solve the situation above, he needs to have clocks at each observation points in the stationary system and in the moving system and that all the clocks have to be perfectly synchronized.

5 Einstein Thought Experiments

5.1 Measuring Light from a Moving Train

In 1905, Einstein was wondering how to measure the speed of a light beam when on a moving train. Somebody is on the embankment of a railway track, fire a light beam and measure it's speed to be c . On the train somebody make the measurement on the same light beam. In order to calculate the speed of the light beam from the train, Einstein uses Galilean's rule for the addition of the velocities of the train and of the light beam. Doing this he could not respect the principle of relativity. Then he uses the so-call Lorentz transformation to respect

the constancy of the speed of light in all reference frames, and give birth to its relativity theory.

There is another way to obtain the same result with much more simplicity, using Young-Sea Huang transformation. Young-Sea Huang transformation render all the laws of physics true in all inertial reference frames, whatever their velocities. It permits to calculate the velocity of the photon fired by the observer at rest on the embankment and the observer in the vehicle. We suppose that the observer at rest on the embankment represent an inertial frame of reference. He can measure the photon velocity that he fired. Let $v=c$ the speed of the photon fired in this reference frame. Also, in this reference frame the velocity of the train passing by is V . The train can also be considered as an inertial frame of reference in which the speed of the fired photon is noted \bar{v} .

Using Young-Sea Huang transformation of velocity from one frame of reference to another one in motion with a velocity V , we get with the preceding notations:

$$v = c \frac{\beta + \bar{v}/c}{1 + \beta\bar{v}/c} \quad (19)$$

With $\beta = V/c$, and since $v=c$, then:

$$\bar{v} = \frac{c(1 - \beta)}{1 - \beta} = c \quad (20)$$

This shows that eventhough the train is going at V , the observer in the train measured the speed of the fired photon on the embankment as c . Moreover, if he fired a second photon is fired from the train at the same instant as the fired photon, the two observers will see the two photons going together at the same speed!

Let's redo this light thought experiment in a different way. Suppose you are on a vehicle going near the speed of light, say $0.9999999999999999 c$ ($9 \times 10^{-15}c$). As you pass near a point in space, someone fire a photon light beam in your direction a few second after. Since the speed of the photon is c , it will overtake your vehicle. The speed difference being $0,0000000000000001 c$ ($10^{-15}c$), the photon will overtake your vehicle at 300 nm every second of duration. Now if you fire a light beam when the first photon is passing by, and supposing photons are created in-situ the ether [5], the two photons will travel at the same speed. If the two photons have the same wave length, the vehicle observer will see them both going away from him fluctuating with the same frequency. Then, with the assumption of emission of a photon in-situ ether, one can demonstrate the possibility to see a photon fluctuating while running side by side, without any problem with relativity.

5.2 Lightning Strikes a Moving Train

Also in 1905, with this thought experiment, Einstein thought that simultaneity is relative and he explained it in the following. Someone is standing on the embankment of a railway track when a train is passing. Each end of this train is struck by a lightning strike just as the train midpoint's is passing by the observer on the embankment. This observer says that the lightning strikes happened simultaneously. Another observer is sitting on the train at the midpoint. Because the train is moving, this observer will conclude that the lightning strokes are not simultaneous. Einstein, taking advantage of this thought experiment base its special relativity theory on the fact that the time given by a clock is local. That is to say that if there are two observers located at points A and B in space, then there is a "A time" and a "B time".

We can think differently about this thought experiment. First of all we have to define what an "instant of time" might be, Einstein using the term "epoch". We define an "instant

of time” as a situation where all the bodies in the universe have their own position perfectly known.

When the lightning strokes occurs at both extremities of the moving train, the observer on the embankment can observe the simultaneity of the lightning flashes by the instant of time of each beam when they reach the observer. But this observer cannot know the origins of the two strokes if nobody tells him it was on the train extremities.

For the observer on the train, he can note the instant of time of the arrival of one of the strokes and the delay for the arrival of the second strokes. Knowing that the train is moving with respect to the embankment he can think of two possibilities:

a) the two lightning strokes are simultaneous and the delay is due only to the motion of the train,

b) the two lightning strokes are not simultaneous because the delay is also due to the non simultaneity of the strokes. Then the observer on the train can't say with certitude that the two lightning strokes are or are not simultaneous. But with the information that the lightning strokes were localized at each end of the train, the observer on the train can conclude, knowing that the speed of light is a constant, that they are simultaneous with a simple calculation. This information can be given to the observer on the train to help him in his conclusion.

Then simultaneity of two events do not depend of the motion of the observer, if all observers are doing the necessary corrections. It depends of more informations.

6 Conclusion

The comparison of the two relativity theories can be summarized by:

-Einstein SR is assuring all the laws of physics to hold good from one frame to another in relative motion by transforming the space time coordinates of a matter point: x, y, z, t .

-Young-Sea Huang is assuring all the laws of physics to hold good from one frame to another in relative motion by transforming the energy-momentum of a particle using the displacement of a matter point: $\delta x^1, \delta x^2, \delta x^3, \delta x^0$.

- Einstein SR is incompatible with quantum mechanics, while Young-Sea Huang is compatible.

- In Einstein SR, time is local, while in Young-Sea Huang time is the Newton time, universal.

- In Einstein SR, a moving vehicle encounter local time dilation and local length contraction, while in Young-Sea Huang it doesn't.

- In Einstein SR, events are not simultaneous in the universe, while in Young-Sea Huang they are.

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